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The influence of very low calorie diet on parameters of metabolic activity of bone

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Abstract

Introduction: Osteoporosis is a systemic skeletal disease characterized by low bone density and changes in microarchitecture of bone, that have resulted in an increased tendency to fractures. On the metabolic activity of bone affect the following factors related to nutritional status: increased body mass, gravity, and the fact that adipose tissue is "metabolic and endocrine organ," which secretes its hormones, mainly estrogen, leptin and adiponectin, that can affect bone metabolic activity.

Objective: was to show whether, and how, rapid weight loss influence on bone metabolism.

Method: The prospective study included 30 women in the generative period hospitalized for obesity treatment with very low calorie diet, which means taking 800 mg of calcium and 500 ij vitamin D daily. Influence of therapy on metabolic bone activity is estimated by analyzing the parameters of bone metabolic activity: osteocalcin, beta cross laps and PTH in serum was measured by "Elecsys" methodology, based on the sandwich immunometric reaction, at the beginning and end of therapy. In the same time, we determined levels of ionized calcium by measuring the potential difference (potentiometry) on an automated analyzer AVL. Nutritional status at the beginning and end of therapy was evaluated based on TM (kg) and BMI (kg / m²), waist circumference and BIA used to evaluate parameters: FAT% (percentage of body fat), FATM (amount of body fat mass in kg) and FFM (percentage of lean body weight in kg).

Results: After treatment there were reduction in body weight (p<0.0063), BMI (p<0.0082), waist circumference (p<0.274), percentage of fat mass (p<0.051), amount of fat mass (p<0.077), and amounts of fat free mass (p<0.075). There was a statistically significant difference in parameters of bone resorption at the end of treatment compared

to initial values - CrossLaps (p<0.005) and ionized calcium (p <0.009). Serum osteocalcin (p<0.667) and PTH (p<0.430) were not significantly changed during treatment.

Conclusion: The regime of very low calorie diet leads to increased bone resorption, with unchanged bone formation, resulting in increased serum calcium from bone tissue, probably caused short and reversible engagement of PTH.

Key words: bone metabolism, bone remodeling, very low calorie diet

Introduction

Osteoporosis is a systemic skeletal disease characterized by reduction in bone density and changes in bone microarchitecture, that results in increased propensity to fractures. [1,2,3] According to the National Osteoporosis Foundation in 2004 in the United States has 10 million people with from osteoporosis and 34 million people who are predisposed to get osteoporosis. [4] The consequences of untreated osteoporosis are different location of fractures, usually distal radius, spine and hip, which can occur with a small trauma, pain, inability to perform common daily physical activities, dependence on others, depression, anxiety, isolation, and even increased mortality compared with persons of the same age. [3]

The main pathogenetic factors for osteoporosis are menopause in women and the aging process, but many other factors have influence on its contribute to its occurrence. According to the Grujic et al, 63,2% people older than 20 years wrongly assess their nutritional status [4]. One factor is certainly underweight, a BMI below 21kg/m² [6], till the obesity is a protective factor for osteoporosis [7] At the same time, obesity is a significant independent risk factor for cardiovascular disease,

diabetes and breast cancer, that it must be treated. The question is whether weight reduction causes changes in bone remodeling with domination bone resorption over formation, that lead an increased risk of osteoporosis. Some results show that 5-10% weight loss leads to a significant reduction in bone mass (8,9).

Several factors related to nutritional status may influence bone remodeling. First, it is gravity which influence on osteocyte's mechanoreceptors, the main stimulator of bone formation (7,8). On the other hand, fat as, "metabolic and endocrine organ," which secretes its hormones, mainly estrogen, leptin and adiponectin may affect the metabolic activity of bone.

Objective

The aim of study is to investigate whether changes in body weight, BMI, percentage fat body mass, body fat mass and quantity of fat free mass achieved during low-calorie diet regime impact on bone metabolic activity and on bone formation and resorption parameters.

Method

The a prospective study was done at the Clinic for Endocrinology, Diabetes and Metabolic Diseases at the Clinical Center of Vojvodina in the group of 30 patients in the generative period of life, aged 20-50 years hospitalized for treatment of obesity with BMI over 30 kg/m² during 30 days.

Very low calorie diet during which patients took dietary purchasable product four times a day instead of meal. The total daily intake of nutrients was: 22.4 g protein, 7.8 g. fat, linoleic acid 2.56 g, 60 g carbohydrates, 10.4 g lactose, 8 g dietary fiber, Vitamin A 1.12 mg, vitamin E 34.9 mg, 8.36 mg vitamin B1, vitamin B2 7.24 mg, Vitamin B6 6.98 mg, 6.9 mg vitamin B12, vitamin D3 500 IU, 0.5 mg of fluoride, 8.96 mg of pantothenic acid, folic acid 0.44 mg, 63.44 mg of nicotinamide, biotin 0.336 mg, Vitamin C 189.6 mg, Calcium 802 mg, Phosphorus 480 mg, Magnesium 315 mg, 1002.5 mg of potassium, sodium 592mg, chloride 848mg, iron 21.2 mg, Copper 1.62 mg, Manganese 2.74 mg, 0.05 mg of cobalt, molybdenum 0.1 mg, 96 mg Iodine, zinc 96 mg, 0.12 mg, 1232 mg

isoleucine, leucine 1904 mg, 1512 mg of lysine, tyrosine fenilalnina + 2128 mg + metinina 1400 mg cystine, threonine 940 mg, 300 mg of tryptophan, valine 1360 mg. Patients consumed every day and three to four liters of mineral water and a multivitamin.

Inclusion criteria was:

- females
- The age of 20-50 years
- Have regular menstrual cycles, there are no signs of cardiovascular disease, liver, kidney, CNS, or other endocrine or metabolic disorders (except for hyperlipoproteinemia)
- Have no medication therapy which can have influence on the metabolism of carbohydrates and fats (oral contraceptives, hormone replacement therapy, antihypertensive drugs and other medications)

Non-inclusion cruteria:

- Women with any of the above diseases
- Women who are on medical therapy that can have influence on the metabolism of carbohydrates and fats

Exclusion criteria:

- Fealure to cooperate (non-compliance with prescribed therapy)
- The development of the disease or condition during the tests that could affect the health of patients

In the study were included women who were agree to engage in research with the prior introduction to the work plan, methods and research goals.

Before initiation of therapy and after therapy were measured anthropometric parameters: body mass (TM), body mass index (BMI) and body composition parameters: the percentage of fat body mass (fat%), the amount of fat body mass (FATM) and the amount of lean body mass (FFM). Body composition was determined using BIA (bioelectrical impedance) device Tanita.

First and 30 days of treatment were measured biochemical bone metabolic parameters: osteocalcin (OCL), Cross-Laps (CL) and parathormone (PTH) in serum using "Elecsys" methodology, based on the sandwich imunometric reaction in the ionized calcium (Ca) measured on the basis of potential

difference (potentiometry) on an automated analyzer laboratory equipment manufacturers of AVL.

Data are presented in tables and graphs, and statistical analysis was performed using ANOVA methods, discrimination method, which assessed the statistical significance of observed changes in the numerical characteristics after treatment compared to the values before treatment patients. The significance of differences between measurements subjects before and after treatment was measured by Mannova's method.

Results

The study involved 30 women generative period of life between the ages of 20 and 50 years who were treated with very low calorie diet during 30 days.

The results of anthropometric parameters before and after treatment are shown in Table 1

Table 1. Changes in anthropometric parameters Thought investigation

Parameters	Therapy	x	SD	p
TM (kg)	Before	111.54	18.99	-
	After	102.17	19.38	0.063
BMI (kg/m ²)	Before	40.45	7.74	-
	After	36.93	7.63	0.082

Body weight decreased after treatment for an average of 9.37 kg (8.4%) compared to values before treatment.

The average value of the average reduction in BMI of 3.52 kg / m² (8.7%), which is border of significance.

After statistical processing of data can be seen that the reduction in body weight and BMI at the end of treatment was statistically significantly increased risk compared with the initial values.

Table 2. Changes in body composition parameters of thought investigation

Parameters	Therapy	x	SD	p
FATM % (%)	Before	48.48	4.61	-
	After	45.86	5.54	0.051
FAT (kg)	Before	54.63	14.26	-
	After	47.88	14.77	0.077
FFM (kg)	Before	57.28	5.72	-
	After	54.64	5.54	0.075

Of the total 30 patients, in 29 (97%) was observed FATM% reduction. The average value FATM% statistically significant decrease, in the 2.62 kg (5.4%) compared to initial values.

Also, it was statistically insignificant reduction FATM average of 6.75 kg (12.36%)

The average value of the FFM statistically insignificant decrease of 2.64 (4.75%) compared with initial values.

Graph 1. Percentage fat body mass in women

Of the 30 respondents in 29 (97%) there was a decrease in the percentage of fat body mass

Table 3. Changes in parameters of bone metabolism thought investigation

Parameters	Therapy	x	SD	p
OCL (ng/ml)	Before	17.85	6.50	-
	After	17.14	6.21	0.667
CL (pg/ml)	Before	297.11	112.58	-
	After	387.29	124.31	0.005
PTH (pg/ml)	Before	46.28	17.21	-
	After	49.86	17.64	0.430
Ionized Ca (mmol/l)	Before	0.94	0.05	-
	After	0.98	0.05	0.009

During the research it has been found insignificant reduction in OCL (p <0.667) and PTH nonsignificant increase (p <0.430). Values of Cross-laps and ionized calcium were statistically significantly increased (p less than 0.005 and p less than 0.009)

Graph 2. Confidence interval for Cross-Laps and ionized calcium

Legend: before treatment (1), after treatment (2), Cross-Laps (CL), ionized calcium (Ca)

Discussion

Obesity is an independent risk factor for mass non-communicable diseases such as cardiovascular disease, diabetes and breast cancer. Therefore, the treatment of obesity is considered prevention of these diseases. On the other hand, obesity is considered a protective factor for osteoporosis in postmenopausal women, so the question is whether the treatment of obesity increases the risk of osteoporosis through the imbalance in remodeling of bone, with predominant bone resorption.

It is known that the key risk factor for osteoporosis in menopause. Estrogen deficit accelerated bone resorption, influence on the proinflammatory cytokines TNF-alpha family including RANKL responsible for osteoclastogenesis [10,11] In order to avoid the impact of estrogen deficiency on bone metabolism during treatment of obesity, the examination included a group of 30 women in generative period of life.

The authors in their papers show that during the reduction of body weight by 5-10% there is a significant decrease in bone mass [12] and acceleration of bone resorption. [9,13,14] The risk of bone loss during a diet depends on the initial weight loss, weight loss, age, gender, physical activity and intake of calcium and vitamin D during low-calorie

diet [15] In our study has shown that low-calorie diet with a calcium intake of 800 mg and vitamin D 500 IU leads to a statistically significantly elevated values of Cross Laps-bone resorption parameters, and the initial increase low ionized calcium values, until the value of a parameter of bone formation, osteocalcin, did not change. This finding suggests that the changes in the remodeling of our patients more responsible than applied dietetic regimen reduce the force of gravity and weight. In fact, no one knows the precise mechanism of action of mechanical loads on the bone, but it is assumed that the mechanical stimulus acts on a data network osteocytes, which registers changes in the level of mechanical force and converts them into appropriate signals, which then regulate the metabolic activity of bone. [16,17] There are assumptions that create osteocyt's signal proportional to the mechanical load. It supports premise that women with higher levels of physical and nutritional status have a greater amount of bone mass. Through weight loss women will reduce mechanical stress, and consequently reduce stimulation of bone formation which lead losses of bone mass. Some authors assume that the rate of bone loss after weight loss result of stress on the bones was due to reduced loads on the bone. [18] The absence of reduction in bone formation in our work can be attributed: 1) insufficient degree of reduction of body weight achieved a treatment, 2) the follow-up period of 30 days is too short for a definitive assessment of effects on osteoblasts and whose life and the ultimate effect on bone formation takes several months.

That a daily intake of calcium and vitamin D probably as well as their intestinal absorption is important for the effect of weight loss on bone metabolism and bone mass showed numerous authors. Parameters of bone metabolism during weight reduction are significantly greater in women who did not receive therapy during Ca supplementation, compared with the group that received 1.7 g Ca daily. [19,20] Ricci et al noted that during starvation there was a statistically significant increase of bone resorption parameters (deoxypyridinolin and piridinolin) and increasing the value of statistical nonsignificant PTH and osteocalcin, as shown in our work. [14] The initial low values of ionized with insufficient calcium intake of 800 mg daily intake during the regime of low-calorie

diet, may lead to short-term engagement PTH in terms of increased tubular reabsorption of calcium and/or to increased mobilization of calcium from bone by stimulating osteoclasts and depots as evidenced by statistically significant increase in Cross Laps. Otherwise, the low level of calcium is not surprising. In the NHANES III study was observed that as much as 50% of female generative period in the United States takes less than 600 mg of calcium per day and has low levels of calcium in the blood. [21]

However, it is known that fat is "metabolic and endocrine" organ in which, among other things, produce or secrete hormones such as estrogen, leptin, and adiponectin. It is known that obese people have a much greater amount and percentage of body fat mass. Adipocytes secrete leptin, a hormone which are currently not well understood mechanism is operating in the center of hunger and satiety in the hypothalamus and is one of the key regulators of nutritional status. The concentration of leptin is significantly different among individuals and correlates with the degree of nutritional status. It is known that leptin levels positively correlated with fat% [22,23,24]. It is possible that the anabolic effect of leptin on bone influences the positive correlation between bone mass and FATM. Obese people have significantly higher concentrations of leptin than normal weight individuals. [22,23,24] By reducing the level of nutrition and reduces the concentration of leptin in the blood. In the literature it has been observed statistically significant decrease in leptin concentrations during the weight reduction. [22] Although not yet know the exact mechanism of action of leptin on bone, previous research suggests that leptin affects the differentiation of osteoblasts, and that there is no direct effect on osteoclasts. [25] It is thought that leptin has a dual role in bone metabolism: central, it inhibits bone formation through effects on the hypothalamus, while its peripheral role increases the creation of OPG (Osteoprotegerin) in osteoblasts. OPG secreted by osteoblasts can bind to RANKL and inhibit action RANK-a, and thus inhibit the osteoclasts differentiation. Peripheral role of Leptin si to increases the level of OPG, a higher concentration of leptin and higher mean concentrations of OPG, which significantly reduces the degree of bone resorption. In our work,

as in the literature [25,26] observed a statistically significant decrease in FFM than FATM modified through starvation which would reduce the level of leptin was partly responsible for the decreased levels of inhibition of bone resorption parameters contributing to the growth of absorption Cross Laps at the end of treatment.

Regardless of the apparently "communication" between the metabolism of fat and bone tissue, one of the offered solutions for the prevention of increased bone resorption that occurs during the implementation low calorie diet in our patients is an additional supplementation of calcium and possibly vitamin D. For this intervention is advocated by other authors. Riedt et al. in their work recognized that in patients taking 1.7 g of calcium per day has been reduced or trochanter BMD or BMC, and spine, as opposed to women who consumed 1 g per day of Ca, where the observed significant reduction in BMD (4%) and BMC (5%) from baseline values. [20] It is also the patients who did not receive further observed a significant increase in Ca parameters of bone resorption, and PTH than in the group that received supplementation of Ca. It was observed that the women that are in addition to 800 mg Ca (who consumed diet) consumed 1 g Ca even further, there were no changes in the amount of bone mass, in contrast to other groups of women who did not receive supplementation of Ca where there has been a significant decrease of bone mass. [27] The group to which Ca was added and reduction was observed during PTH treatment, which explains the fact that a sufficient quantity of either entering Ca prevented increase PTH and consequently prevented bone resorption. Several authors suggest that the Ca intake of 1.6 grams per day for the restrictive child stabilized PTH levels and prevent bone resorption. Moreover, it appears that increased Ca intake may increase bone mass by 1.7% despite the reduction of weight. [27].

Conclusion

During 30 days of low calorie diet treatment there was reduction in body weight, BMI, percent body fat mass, fat body mass quantities and amounts of lean mass. Differences in body mass, fat percentage and amount of body mass and BMI are borderline statistical significance.

Low calorie diet regimen administered in the manner as shown in our trial, leading to increased bone resorption, with unchanged bone formation, resulting in an increase initially low ionized calcium, possibly caused transient and reversible engagement at the level of PTH renal tubule and osteoclast activity.

Since there is a negative correlation between the decrease in body weight and bone resorption, and given the absence of changes in bone formation, the obtained results it follows that the dominant influence bone metabolism of calcium and possibly vitamin D during the regime of low calorie diet, rather than changes in the state nutritional status.

Additional supplementation of calcium and possibly vitamin D during the low calorie diet, it is possible to order to prevent stimulation of bone resorption and restore balance with bone formation.

In further studies would be necessary for more monitoring of parameters of bone remodeling during and after low calorie diet regime as well as after completion of treatment of obesity. We should take into account changes in other parameters such as leptin, adiponectin and vitamin D as well as changes in bone mass.

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